

Steady Stream Versus the Continuity Equation and Quantum Mechanics

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If one observes a segment of space of length L which has particles entering at $x=0$ and leaving at $x=L$ then even though there are clearly dynamics present, a coarse graining of the scenario within L would suggest no changes in x and t (for one dimension). This coarse graining seems to be equivalent to one not being able to follow a single particle in time and to describing the system in terms of a statistical quantity, namely the number of particles in each dx . In other words, such a picture is static, yet one has underlying dynamics.

We suggest that a particle is described by a p (momentum) and an energy (E) and that a continuity equation describes changes in a region dx , i.e. d/dt partial density (momentum or energy) + grad dot density velocity = 0. This, however, describes changing density. In fact, we suggest that the density is changing due to outgoing particles, but also changing due to incoming ones, so one may look for two solutions to the continuity equation which undo each other to create the sense of no change.

These abstract solutions are $A \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ and $A \exp(-i\omega t - ikx)$. If $\omega = E$ and $k = p$, one has a solution consistent with a photon. The point is that $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ is complex and does not describe the steady stream scenario unless one uses: $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx) * \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$, where $*$ is the complex conjugate. In other words, the continuity equation is a classical one, but has abstract math solutions. These solutions should be linked to the steady stream picture, we argue, because one again is not following each particle in space-time (as one does in classical mechanics), but is rather using a statistical type of description.

In other words, a steady stream picture is statistical in that it does not follow each particle and does not seem to sense any changes in x , t if only a segment is considered. The underlying continuity equation and a solution, $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$, however, allows for different steady streams to be linked at the $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ level (as in the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem). The question then becomes: Why would one wish to use a statistical approach in the first place if classical mechanics allows one to follow each particle through $x(t)$? Even though this is true, if one has a discontinuity in p at $x=0$, as in one dimensional reflection-refraction, probability enters which is not part of the classical mechanical scenario (and would need to be modeled independently). In the case of continuity, one has both continuity of energy and momentum and this allows for the description of probability because two continuity solutions, one for E and one for p may be used. In other words, various $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ s may be matched together with a matching of the first derivative at a discontinuity point. This yields two equations which may solve for two unknowns which may be linked to two probabilities.

In other words, a classical type picture, albeit statistical with steady streams and continuity, seems to lead to a quantum mechanical solution, if one is willing to accept $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ as a solution to the continuity equation. This solution does not appear to be physical if one considers the steady stream (not following single particles) to be the physical reality, but nevertheless describes underlying dynamics.

Classical Mechanics and Steady Stream Motion

Classical mechanics follows each particle in space-time through $x(t)$. The notion of a steady stream exists in classical mechanics and if one can identify each particle and follow its motion, then one describes each particle and not a density of the system. On the other hand, if one considers the particles to all be identical, then one may describe a density at various t values. If the density (spatial) is the same for all t , then it is as if one has a static situation (although there are clearly dynamics). This static scenario (at least for a spatial segment L), however, becomes the physical reality as described by the statistical spatial density description.

Bringing in Dynamics

If the physical reality of a steady stream described by a spatial density is that of no change in x, t and if one cannot follow each particle through $x(t)$, then how does one describe motion in the system? This motion clearly exists, but it cannot be described on a single particle level and so has to be considered in an abstract manner so as not to destroy the physical reality described by the spatial steady stream density picture.

It is well known in classical mechanics that one may have a continuity equation if one has many particles and deals with density and not each particle through $x(t)$, i.e.

$$d/dt \text{ partial density (energy or momentum)} + \text{grad dot density velocity} = 0 \quad ((1))$$

We suggest that there exist both energy and momentum continuity equations. In such a case, ((1)) shows how density may change due to a flux carrying out energy or momentum. The steady stream picture, however, does not have any physical change in density (momentum or energy) at x because particles that leave are replaced by incoming ones. ((1)) only shows particles leaving, otherwise the density would not change in time at a fixed x .

It does, however, seem possible to consider particles coming in and out at the same time with the continuity equation ((1)) applying to both. In particular, $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ is a solution of ((1)), but is complex and may seem unphysical. If $\omega = e$ and $p = k$, then $E = pc$ which applies to a photon. We note that $\exp(-iEt - ipx)$ is a solution for a time reversed picture, i.e. the particles being replenished. If one combines:

$$\exp(-iEt + ipx) \exp(-iEt + ipx) \text{ then density} = \text{constant which is the steady stream result} \quad ((2))$$

but $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt - ipx)$ represent the two flows which create the steady stream picture which appears to be static.

Thus, we argue that one may have an abstract solution describing dynamics in a steady stream statistical picture which appears to have no change in x or t .

Why Does One Want a Steady Stream Picture with an Underlying Dynamic One?

Why should one use such a statistical picture in the first place if deterministic $x(t)$ for each particle is sufficient? It seems that physically deterministic $x(t)$ is not sufficient. For example, in a one dimensional reflection-refraction problem, one has a probability for an incident photon to reflect or refract. In classical mechanics, it seems that one would need to model this probability based on properties of the n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction. The abstract continuity picture, however, has built in probability because one may write two continuity equation, one for energy and the other for momentum:

$$EA \exp(-iEt+ipx) + EB \exp(-iEt-ix) = EC \exp(-iEt+ip2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((3a))$$

$$Ap \exp(-iEt+ipx) - pB \exp(-iEt-ix) = C \exp(-iEt+ip2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((3b))$$

If A is set to 1, one may solve for B and C. It was already argued that AA or BB or CC describe the steady stream flux picture, so AA/c, BB/c and CC/c² represent the incident number of particles, reflected and refracted.

In other words, using energy and momentum continuity allows for two equations which may solve for two unknowns which may be two probabilities.

Why Does the Continuity Equation Lead to Gradations in Time and Space?

It may be seen that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ represents gradations in time and space, namely constant/ E and constant/p or more specifically using $\exp(-i\omega t+ikx)$ and $E=\hbar\omega$ where $\omega=2\pi f$, the gradations are \hbar/E and \hbar/p . These gradations follow from the periodic nature of the solution to the continuity equation. This periodic like solution is required so that one may multiply a p solution with its time reversed one to freeze out motion as per the steady stream scenario. In other words, one has to physically undo a pattern in space. At first one might think that one may undo a smooth function, but $\exp(i\theta)$ has θ as the smooth variable. Classically, $x=vt$ represents smooth motion, but this means following each particle in space and is not statistical.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that if one considers a steady stream classically and does not follow motion of each particle, but rather describes the situation statistically, then the physical reality is one of a static spatial density in time. There is, however, physical motion occurring. Usually, a change in density is described by a continuity equation: d/dt partial density (momentum or energy) + grad dot density $v = 0$. Here, one has no density change which is really a combination of particles flowing in and others out. We suggest then two abstract solutions, $\exp(-i\omega t+ikx)$ and $\exp(-i\omega t-ikx)$ to describe both of these. One is the time reversal of the other. If $\omega=E$ and $k=p$, then $E=pc$ which describes a photon and $\exp(-iEt+ipx)\exp(iEt+ipx)=1$ describes the steady stream. We suggest that such an approach automatically creates time and spatial gradations

due to the periodic nature of the solution which is required so that one solution may undo the other (i.e. the time reversed undo the non-time reversed one). We suggest that by having both momentum and energy continuity, one may write two equations which allow one to solve for two unknowns which allows one to model probability (if there are two) as in the one-dimensional reflection-refraction problem.